

Employees' Participation in Decision Making: A Policy Tool for Corporate Goal Sustainability of Construction Firms in Rivers State

Presented by

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Abstract

This study was carried out to ascertain how employees' participation acts as a strategic policy decision for corporate goal sustainability of construction firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. The study was necessitated as a result of increase man-hour losses and idle time which was occasioned by union activities and loggerheads with management. This was hinged on the premise that management has deliberately avoided employees' contribution on issues that concern their welfare and wellbeing in the organizations studied. However, several works had been carried out on the subject, but there still exist areas that needed the combination of delegation and joint consultation among firms in the road construction industry. The study was accomplished with the use of a well-structured questionnaire of fourteen (14) question items administered to the sample size of 324 respondents drawn from 4 major construction firms in Rivers State. Pearson Product Moment statistical tool was used to test the hypotheses. The findings of this study revealed that, there is a positive significant relationship between the dimensions of both independent and dependent variables stated in the study. Finally, conclusion was drawn that, a participatory decision-making system which are measures whereby employees can be involved in the making of decisions affecting their welfare should be adopted by managers. It further recommended among others that, monthly or quarterly meetings and consultations with subordinates on crucial issues can stimulate employees morale and promote self-motivation as they will feel recognized and valued in the organization, hence should be adopted by managers.

Keywords: Participation, Joint Consultation, Delegation, Deputation,

1.1 Background of the Study

For the years past, organizational management practice demanded that employers/ management ordinarily, anticipate that workers will do the work that is put before them. Although this was perfectly a typical method of getting results through others in the early days of assembly line and scientific management, it is no longer accurate for today's business (Zenieni, et al., 2020). The trend has changed in favour of management expecting more from its employees than doing merely what is placed before them. It has also changed in that workers expect that more can be gotten from them than by simply working according to the directives of the boss. Employees' participation in decision making has emerged as a managerial tool for improving organizational performance by striving for the shared goals of employees and managers (Ojokuku & Sajuyigbe, 2014). The foregoing is actualized by way of allowing workers' input in developing the mission statement, establishing policies and procedures, pay determination, promotion, and determining perks. Celestine & Gramine, (2018) aver that employee participation in decision making has become a significant topic in human resource management (HRM), and is regarded as one of the chief ingredients of employee voice, which many management scholars have observed to be a rising management concept. For instance the Japanese household name and business success rate amongst many countries of the world is attributed to employee participation in decision making, whereby decision making is shared at all levels of management.

In Nigeria, participatory management has come a long way. Oninoukar & Kalabor (2019) pointed that, the Nigeria Military Government in 1977 decided to democratize industrial ownership in Nigeria by promulgating the Nigerian Indigenization Decree, part of which provides "that 10 percent total equity share of any enterprise on the Schedule, 2 and 3 should be reserved for the workers".

Participative decision-making can be well practiced only in a stable economic environment because of its time consuming nature and investment in training to enable workers have contributing capabilities. Metulade, & Freeman (2010) opined in their view that, participative decision-making can be possible in a certain sector of the economy and not in all government-owned enterprises, because of the government intention to mobilize popular support for development purposes. The authors further assert that workers participation in the multinational companies, on the other hand has at best remained elusive. This was owed partly to the fact that most of these companies are controlled by and depend on their parent bodies abroad for policies and decisions. Among the indigenous employers, particularly the small and medium sized organizations, management's attitude to workers is paternalistic and based on authoritarianism (Sahoo, & Mishra, 2020).

Rivers State is arguably, among the fastest developing states in the South-South Zone of Nigeria, characterized by ongoing construction works and developmental projects, occasioning the growth and settlement of both new and renounced construction firms in the State; thus compelling the researcher's interest which was centered on road construction firms which are twenty eight (28) in number as at the time of the study (finelib.com/roadconst.firm.rivstate.2022). Out of these companies, four (4) road construction companies operating in Rivers State, South-South Zone of Nigeria were selected for this study. This was not based on convenience only, but on their spread and operational profile (in terms of experience, quality of work and completion of deliverables) around the country Nigeria, as well as their employees' size. The firms are Julius Berger (JBCC) Nigeria Limited, Raynolds Construction Company (RCC), Lubrick Construction Company (LCC) Nigeria, and Monier Construction Company (MCC). It was against this background that the researcher found it necessary to study

employee participation and organizational success of these (four) construction firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

1:2 Statement of the Problem

Although modern management insists on the importance of employees' participation in decision-making, many private and public enterprises in Nigeria are still being administered on the basis of a traditional approach or rather on the earlier approaches of management which relied more upon autocratic style. Tarima, & Blessing (2010) opined that, in practice, the task of decision-making seemed to be a task of top management. Hence, the deliberate exclusion of employees in the making of decisions that directly affect their well-being and welfare, in the organization of study has increasingly lowered their success factor in the areas of goal accomplishment, customers' satisfaction, and profitability. These were premised on the inability of management to joint consult, delegate, and even accept deputation. Although, researchers have contributed much on the subject, but there still exists gaps that has necessitated further study. Such previous studies abound as that of Olajide, (2019), whose study was hinged on cause and effect, with the use of multiple regression analyses; Nwanah, et al., (2019) whose work was based on comparative measures with the use of analyses of variance as the statistical tool; Precious, et al., (2020) adopted the least square method and simple linear regression analysis, while Chukwuemeka, (2020) carried out a time series analysis with the aim of finding difference in employee action towards management in their non-involvement in decisions for the period of 10 years in the manufacturing sector. This study carefully undertakes a relationship assesrment of employees' participation dimensions against corporate goals dimensions in the road construction industry in Rivers State, with the use of correlation statistical tool.

1.3 Aim and Objectives

The general aim of the study was to determine how employee participation correlates with organizational success in the studied organizations. Specifically, the study sets out:

1. To determine how joint consultation correlates with goal accomplishment in the studied organizations
2. To determine how delegation correlates with customer satisfaction in the studied organizations
3. To determine how deputation correlates with profitability in the studied organizations

1.4 Conceptual Review

In most organizations where management structure is very complex, or tied with international affiliation, decisions are basically restricted to the management level without the inclusion or with the exception of employees in decision-making. Decision-making has been defined by different authors or writers in varying ways. Chizie, & Kalebor (2018) define Decision-making as “the process of identifying and selecting a course of action to solve a particular problem.” It can also be defined as a thought process of selecting a logical choice from the available options in decision-making process. Egbo, (2016) sees decision-making as a process of defining problems and choosing a course of action from the alternatives generated.

Godwin, (2018) asserts that decision-making is at the core of planning. He goes further to elaborate on the fact that a plan cannot be said to exist unless a decision - a commitment of resources, direction, or reputation has been made. So, “decision-making is the commitment of organizational resources to a particular line of action”. Decision-making in this regard is the centerpiece of any management undertaking which must involve managerial use of creativity subjectivity, rationality and at times, some quantitative approaches to issues of corporate, group or individual significance. Omolayo (2016) asserted that, the ultimate aim is to generate, relevant alternatives, pruning them, and then making an intelligent choice. The need for decision-making

is so pervasive that it may be considered as an important part of the managerial job. Thus, managers have to decide how to plan, organize, staff, control and direct organizational activities in order to meet the targeted objectives.

EMPLOYEE PARTICIPATION

Employee participation can be conceptualized as those initiatives which attract the employees to participate voluntarily in organizational activities through various awards and rewards. It connotes also the various means by which employees are involved in the making of decisions that affect their welfare and wellbeing at the workplace. Employees' participation is manifested in the following ways:

Employee Ownership: Through various schemes employees can hold shares of the organization and thus enjoy the usual rights of a shareholder (Orukwo, 2017). This enhances the mutual responsibilities of both the organization and employees on account of being shareholders, employees perform optimally towards greater scales of organizational success as that would reflect in their individual value as well. "Esopa in the US and UK are frequently cited as having a triad of objectives: to broaden the ownership base, stimulate investment and improve performance" (Lewin, & Mitchell, 2017).

Profit Sharing: This is generally done in the form of payment of bonus in proportion to the organization's annual profit. This is a form of employee incentive which intends to enhance employees' commitment (Okeke, 2019).

IMPORTANCE OF EMPLOYEE PARTICIPATION

Too often, companies fall into the habit of making plans and creating strategies without the input of the people who will be working to achieve these objectives. But the link between employee

voice and organization performance is absolute. Encouraging your team to have a voice and guide high-level strategies will show your employees just how much you value their opinions and help you identify new and innovative ways to progress your company (Amiete, 2018).

Joint Consultation

In defining “joint consultation” and “participation” Alibor, (2019) pointed out that, we must ask two questions; first, do managers relate to workers individually or collectively through their representatives; and second, are workers passive recipients of information about the practice of health and safety management or can they actively influence its direction? The answers lie in two different approaches. One has its origin in the idea of collective worker rights, the other in the idea of advancing a co-operative dialogue between workers and managers (Benson, & Ovuru, 2020). While the former was behind campaigns that led to specific legislative measures on worker representation on health and safety in some countries, the latter has been dominant in their implementation. To understand these differences it is necessary to first consider so-called “direct participation” before discussing the meaning of collective representation.

Deputation Participation

This is either voluntary or statutorily mandated under ILO Convention 155 and international regulations such as the EU Framework Directive 89/391. Alibor, (2019) observed that, they generally provide for a number of minimum legal rights for effective worker representation through:

- a. Selection of representatives in health and safety by workers
- b. Protection of representatives from victimization or discrimination as a result of their representative role

- c. Paid time off to be allowed to carry out the function of safety representative
- d. Paid time off to be trained in order to function as a safety representative (Arifa, et al., 2019)
- e. The right to receive adequate information from the employer on current and future hazards to the health and safety of workers at the workplace
- f. The right to inspect the workplace
- g. The right to investigate complaints from workers on health and safety matters
- h. The right to make representations to the employer on these matters (Odero, & Makori, 2017)
- i. The right to be consulted over health and safety arrangements, including future plans
- j. The right to be consulted about the use of specialists in health and safety by the employer
- k. The right to accompany health and safety authority inspectors when they inspect the workplace and to make complaints to them when necessary (Abdulai & Shafiwu, 2014).

Amah, et al., (2018) noted that, there are two ways in which the operation of representative worker participation can be understood. The first is rooted in representation of workers by organized labor in and out of the workplace and linked historically to the development of collective labor rights and the institutions of socially democratic welfare societies. Examples are agreements negotiated by trade unions with employers, national labor legislation, and international provisions such as ILO Convention 155 and the EU Framework Directive, which are often the consequence of trade union political campaigns.

Delegation

Delegation is transfer of authority. Ubenita, (2016) defined delegation as the downward transfer of authority from a superior to a subordinate. Desmond et al., (2019) asserted that, delegation

important is because the superior cannot look after all the processes. Chukwuemeka & Carmoli, (2018) also posited that, delegation helps him manage his work, as it is impractical for a specific superior to handle the volume of work all by himself. Anocle, (2019) stated that delegation of authority allows for concentration of time on more important activities in an organization. Further, Chermiss, & Kalu, (2017) states that, it provides a sense of responsibility, a chance to grow and exercise initiatives to whom the authority is delegated.

Soleovie, & Iyerkue, (2019) observed that, one important point to remember is that transfer of authority from a superior to a subordinate does not mean a transfer of accountability. Interestingly, the accountability for the tasks still resides with the superiors. Effectively, delegation involves the distribution of authority for less important jobs to subordinates accompanied by no transfer of accountability (Ugwu, et. al., 2019).

Importance of Delegation

Effective Management: Delegation provides a breathing space to managers by sharing their workload. As a result, managers can concentrate on tasks with higher priority. Further, freedom from routine work allows for exploration of new ideas (Armstrong et al. 2016; in Matilda, & Lawson, 2018).

Employee Development: With the help of delegation, we assign new responsibilities to employees. Ofoegbu, et al., (2013) posited that, this allows for them to work on a domain which is different from the monotonous routine work, helping them to develop new skills and discover hidden talents (Lewin & Mitchell, 2017).

Motivation of Employees: Through the process of delegation, superiors entrust suitable subordinates with the tasks that are assigned to them. This not only leads to the development of talent but also has various psychological benefits (Mimonter, 2018).

Facilitation of Growth: As mentioned, delegation provides employees with opportunities to develop and effectively train them as better decision-makers and managers (Ukaban, et. al., 2020).

Management Hierarchy: Delegation establishes the superior-subordinate relationship. Also, Passmore, & Fagans, (2020) argued that, it is directly related to the extent and flow of authority. This is because authority determines who has to report to whom.

LEADERSHIP

Leadership is the life blood of any organization and its importance cannot be underestimated. Many authors have studied this phenomenon, but there is no universally acceptable definition of what leadership is, no dominant paradigm for studying it, and little agreement regarding the best strategies for developing and exercising it (Martins, & Peace, (2017). Omolayo (2006) views leadership as that kind of direction, which a person can give to a group of people under him in such a way that these will influence the behavior of another individual, or group. Therefore leadership is the exertion of influence over the behavior of a person or group of persons. One best way of exerting leadership by an employer over his / her employees is through the involvement of employees in the determination of what affects them in the organizational relationship that binds them together.

1.7 Empirical Review

Barkosi, (2018) studied participatory decision-making and organizational goal attainment. The study found out thus: employee participation in decision-making significantly improves job performance ($X^2_{cal} = 2.554 > X^2_{0.5} = 0.6763$); employee participation in decision-making

relates to employee motivation ($F_{c} - \text{test} = 21.56 > f_{t1} = 2.01$); the policy of employee participation in decision-making is significant in organizational goal attainment ($X^2_{\text{Cal}} = 1.887 > X^2_{0.5} = 0.6763$). Chigozie, (2019), studied if Employees' Participation in Decision-Making Increases the level of Corporate Social and Environmental Sustainability. The findings demonstrated that employee participation has a strong positive effect on all the components of sustainability (environmental and societal).

Owolabi and Abdul-Hameed, (2011), examines the relationship between employee involvement in decision-making and firms' performance in the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. Data were generated by means of questionnaires to 670 manufacturing firms on employee involvement in decision-making and performance variables. Responses from the survey were statistically analysed using descriptive statistics, product moment correlation, regression analysis and Z-test (approximated with the independent samples t-test). The findings also revealed a positive influence recorded as a result of the practice of participating firms in employee involvement in decision-making. The implications of the study include the need for manufacturing firms to demonstrate high level of commitment to employee involvement in decision-making for performance enhancement.

Shina, et al., (2018), investigated the existing level of worker participation in management decision-making within the Indian work environment. The study involved a survey in which a total of 217 non-management employees drawn from two work organizations in Uttar Pradesh (Flour Mills and Sugar Mills) were used as subjects. The study reveals a growing desire of non-management employees in the Indian work environment to exercise greater involvement in the decision-making process of their enterprises.

Oninoukar, & Kalabor, (2019), investigated the relationship between employee involvement (EI) and organizational productivity (OP). The possible moderating effect of organizational commitment (OC) was also considered. The four employee involvement elements (power, information, knowledge/skills, and rewards) were examined, and propositions were provided concerning the influence of these elements on organizational productivity, and the interaction between these elements and organizational commitment that affects organizational productivity. A conceptual model, implications, and suggestions for future inquiry were presented.

1.5 Theoretical Review

This study is anchored on Human Relation Theory by George Elton Mayo in 1948, and Democratic Participatory Theory propounded by Jean-Jacques Rousseau in the 18th Century, and promoted by John Stuart Mill in 1873. The Human Relations Theory stems from the understanding that the cooperation of workers is desirable for the attainment of the objectives of high productivity and industrial peace. It contends that workers would-be better motivated if they are treated like human beings rather than as irrational objects. For instance, by making them have a feeling that the organization accords them recognition by involving them in the decision-making process. In the light of the theory, the worker is to be perceived in terms of his membership of a social group rather as an individual, Martins, et al., (2018). The Democratic Participatory Theory emphasizes on conditions which are necessary for effective participation and functions performed by participation to the individuals and society. For instance, Nwanah. et al., (2019), contended that through participation in decision-making, the individual sense of freedom is increased since it gives the worker a very real degree of control over the course of his life and structure of his environment. Again, it serves to increase the value of individual freedom

by enabling him to be his own master. Mills (1965) in Ogonagu, & Tayo, (2017), sees the industry as an area where the individual could gain experience in the management of the collective just as he could in government. In essence, greater participation in one sense of life leads to greater participation in other spheres, i.e., the workplace (Nwoko & Emerole, 2017).

Also adopted was the Life Circle Theory of Leadership propounded in 1972 by Paul Hersey and Kenneth H. Blanchard. The theory based its assumption on the fact that appropriate leader behavior depends on the maturity of the leader's followers. He defined maturity as the extent to which the subordinate is motivated, competent, experienced and willing to take on responsibility. Their assumption was founded on four major styles: telling, selling, participation, and delegation (Orukwo, 2017).

The study was further anchored on the Subjective Expected Utility theory (SEU) developed by L. J. Savage in 1954. The theory holds that a rational agent always attempts to maximize its reward by choosing the action with the highest expected utility. The theory of subjective expected utility combines two subjective concepts; first, a personal utility function, and second a personal probability distribution (usually based on Bayesian probability theory) (in Ukaban, et al., 2020). It is inferred therefrom that the quality of human capital available in organizations reflects the quality of decisions and choices made, thus such decisions ultimately result in organization performance (Tarima, & Blessing, 2018).

1.6 Research Design

The study adopted the correlation research design. This method was considered appropriate because it enabled the researcher to have a direct contact with respondent in cause of data collection. There was the use of a structured questionnaire as primary source of data. Also, the

analytical technique adopted for the study was the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient. The population of the study was 1700 employees of the four (4) construction firms in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The sample size for the study was 324 chosen based on the Taro Yamen formula in line with proportional sampling technique

Table 1 Correlation Matrix of Bivariate Analyses

		Joint Consultatio n	Delegation	Deputation	Goal Accomplishmen t	Customer Satisfaction
Joi nt Co ns ult	r- Value					
	2-taile d					
Del eg ati on	r- Value	0.79				
	2-taile d	0.000				
De put ati on	r- Value	.738**	.802**			
	2-taile d	0.000	0.000			
Go al Ac co mp lish	r- Value	.496**	.510**	.452**		
	2-taile d	0.000	0.000	0.000		
Cu sto me rs Sat isfa ctio n	r- Value	.503**	.388**	.389**	.498**	
	2-taile d	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	
Pro fita bilit y	r- Value	.582**	.476**	.480**	.669**	.794**
	2-taile d	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	324	324	324	324	324

Source: SPSS 25.00 Output. Field Survey, (2022).

Table 1 Showed the Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) on the relationship between variables of the study.

1.7 Discussion of Findings

From analysis of the data, findings revealed that all the studied dimensions of the independent variables (joint consultation, delegation, and deputation) correlates with the studied dimensions of the dependent variable namely, goal accomplishment, customer's satisfaction, and profitability; at a least measure $0.36r > 0.00p$. Thus, from the research hypothesis one tested and analyzed, it was revealed that there is a significant relationship between consultation and goal accomplishment in the studied organization, which corroborates Doris, & Eze, (2017) prior observations. Also, from the test of the hypothesis 2, it was clear that employees' participation through delegation contributes positively towards the overall growth of the organization and also helps in enhancing its development in terms of work environment; as well as customer's satisfaction and productivity (Iwokiri, 2018). Lastly, from the hypothesis three, findings revealed that there is a positive significant relationship between deputation and profitability in the studied organizations.

1.8 Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concludes that employees' participation in decision-making has a significantly positive effect on organizational productivity. Generally it can be said that participatory decision-making system requires measures which executive managers should consider, by deliberately taking measures to reinforce the goals, values and responsibilities thereby sustaining the expectations. Monthly or quarterly meetings and consultations with subordinates on crucial

issues should be encouraged, as these will stimulate employee morale and promote self-motivation, given that employees will feel recognized and valued in the organization. The managers and leaders in the organization must encourage employee involvement during quarterly meetings, weekly strategic sessions and team building sessions or interaction sessions, employees must be encouraged to address concerns relating to their jobs or share ideas on how to improve existing policies, practices and procedures that can improve performance levels. The organization must exhibit a high level of commitment to its employees; this is because if employees are concerned about losing their jobs, there will be very little likelihood of high level of employees' commitment.

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